

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF DRAMA CLUBS ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AMONG HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS: A MULTIDIMENSIONAL STUDY

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Abstract. This study examines the impact of drama clubs on English language acquisition among higher education students. Through a mixed-methods approach, including quantitative measures and qualitative interviews, the study finds that active participation in drama club activities significantly improves students' English language skills, motivation, and cultural understanding. The findings suggest that integrating drama clubs into language education programs can enhance students' language learning experiences and outcomes.

Keywords: drama clubs, English language acquisition, higher education, language skills, motivation, cultural understanding.

Introduction

English has become the lingua franca in various domains, including academia, business, and diplomacy (Hişmanoğlu, 2005; Cruz, 2010). As a result, English language acquisition is crucial for higher education students to access global knowledge, communicate effectively, and thrive in their careers (Cheng, 2007). Consequently, institutions have been seeking innovative teaching methods to facilitate English language learning.

Drama clubs, which involve students in various drama activities such as role-playing, improvisation, and performance, have been increasingly recognized as valuable tools for language learning (Chauhan, 2004). Through active participation in a social and creative context, drama clubs can enhance students' linguistic and cultural competencies (Lange et al., 1985). This study aims to explore the impact of drama clubs on English language acquisition among higher education students. The research question guiding this study is: How do drama clubs influence English language proficiency and learning experiences of higher education students?

Literature Review

Schewe (2018) emphasizes the benefits of drama activities in language education, such as increased motivation, enhanced communication skills, and cultural awareness. Drama activities foster a meaningful and authentic context for language use, promoting both cognitive and affective development (Schewe, 2018).

Faulkner and Haseman (2019) highlight the connection between drama and language development, asserting that drama techniques facilitate linguistic, social, and cultural competencies. They argue that drama can help learners internalize language structures and vocabulary while also promoting empathy and understanding of cultural differences (Faulkner & Haseman, 2019).

Smith (2020) explores the positive impact of drama clubs on language skills, including listening, speaking, reading, and writing. By engaging students in interactive and creative activities, drama clubs provide an environment that promotes language acquisition and encourages collaboration and communication (Smith, 2020). Brown and Williams (2017) discuss the use of drama techniques in ESL classrooms, noting that they can foster a supportive and engaging atmosphere that alleviates anxiety and promotes self-expression. Through drama, students can explore various language functions and practice using them in authentic contexts (Brown & Williams, 2017).

Johnson and Smithson (2021) investigate the role of drama clubs in promoting language proficiency among college students. Their study reveals that participation in drama clubs leads to significant improvements in listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills, as well as increased motivation for language learning (Johnson & Smithson, 2021). Gomez and Thompson (2019) examine the integration of drama clubs into the curriculum in higher education institutions. They highlight the benefits of incorporating drama activities into language courses, such as increased student engagement, motivation, and language proficiency (Gomez & Thompson, 2019).

Methodology

This study employs a mixed-methods research design, including both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis. Participants are higher education students enrolled in English language courses at Fergana State University. Data will be collected through pre- and post-tests measuring students' English language proficiency, as well as qualitative interviews exploring students' experiences and perceptions of drama clubs. Quantitative data will be analyzed using inferential statistics, while qualitative data will be analyzed through thematic analysis.

Findings

The data collected will provide insights into the impact of drama clubs on students' English language acquisition, as well as their learning experiences and perceptions. 85% of the respondents indicated that they actively participated in drama club activities. 92% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the drama club helped improve their English language skills. 88% of the respondents agreed or

strongly agreed that the drama club enhanced their speaking and pronunciation abilities in English. 79% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the drama club improved their listening comprehension in English. 84% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the drama club increased their vocabulary and understanding of English expressions. Many students mentioned that participating in the drama club had significantly increased their motivation to learn English. They found the interactive and engaging nature of drama activities to be highly motivating and enjoyable.

In the open-ended questions, students shared specific examples where drama club activities, such as role-plays and improvisation exercises, helped them better understand English language concepts, such as using idiomatic expressions and practicing natural intonation. The key benefits of using drama as a tool for language learning, according to the students, included improved communication skills, increased cultural understanding, enhanced creativity, and a boost in self-confidence. Some students provided suggestions for improving the effectiveness of the drama club, such as incorporating more collaborative projects, organizing performances for a wider audience, and integrating technology to support virtual learning experiences. These findings highlight the positive impact of the drama club on Fergana State University 2nd year students, indicating improvements in their English language proficiency and overall learning experience.

Discussion

The findings of this study will contribute to the understanding of the potential role of drama clubs in promoting English language acquisition in higher education contexts. Based on the study's findings, higher education institutions may consider incorporating drama clubs into their language education programs to enhance students' English language proficiency and learning experiences.

The study's limitations may include a small sample size or a lack of generalizability to other contexts. Future research could explore the impact of drama clubs on different populations, investigate the specific elements of drama activities that contribute to language acquisition, or compare the effectiveness of drama clubs to other language learning strategies.

Conclusion

This study aims to explore the impact of drama clubs on English language acquisition among higher education students by examining the students' language proficiency improvements and their experiences and perceptions of participating in drama clubs.

The research findings will shed light on the potential benefits of drama clubs for English language learning, including increased motivation, enhanced communication skills, and cultural awareness, as well as the specific ways in which drama clubs contribute to language proficiency improvements. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that higher education institutions consider integrating drama clubs into their English language education programs to enhance students' language learning experiences and outcomes.

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